

Appendix A: Injected transmission spectra

Fig. A.1. The model transmission spectra injected into each of the datasets. The top two panels show both the individual species' contributions, as well as the total unbrodened spectrum for $P = 2$ days. The bottom two panels show both the individual species' contributions, as well as the total unbrodened spectrum for $P = 12$ days. The alternating white and grey shaded regions in each of the panels are the individual ESPRESSO orders after pairing, described in Sect. [2.4](#)

Appendix B: Additional relative abundance comparisons

Fig. B.1. Similar to Fig. 4 for DS2.

Fig. B.2. Similar to Fig. 5 for DS2.

Fig. B.3. Similar to Fig. 4 for DS3.

Fig. B.4. Similar to Fig. 5 for DS3.

Appendix C: Atmospheric retrieval corner plots

Fig. C.1. The atmospheric retrieval results for P2 injected into DS1 and preprocessed with SysREM, with the 1D and 2D marginalised posterior distributions of each of the model parameters displayed. The red and blue posterior distributions represent independent subchains, of the same MCMC chain, both converging to similar distributions. The injected values are shown as green vertical/horizontal dashed lines. The T - P profile shown on the right was computed from 10,000 random samples of the MCMC, where the solid red curve shows the median profile, and the grey shaded regions show the 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ contours. The injected profile is shown as a green dashed curve. The cloud deck, located at $\log_{10}(P_{\text{cloud}})$ is highlighted as a blue dotted line. Below this value, the model is truncated, and thus the model inference breaks down. The contribution curve is also shown in blue.

Fig. C.2. Similar to Fig. C.1 for P12.

Fig. C.3. The atmospheric retrieval results for P2 injected into DS1 and preprocessed with MOLECFIT, with the 1D and 2D marginalised posterior distributions of each of the model parameters displayed. The red and blue posterior distributions represent independent subchains, of the same MCMC chain, both converging to similar distributions. The injected values are shown as green vertical/horizontal dashed lines. The T - P profile shown on the right was computed from 10,000 random samples of the MCMC, where the solid red curve shows the median profile, and the grey shaded regions show the 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ contours. The injected profile is shown as a green dashed curve. The cloud deck, located at $\log_{10}(P_{\text{cloud}})$ is highlighted as a blue dotted line. Below this value, the model is truncated, and thus the model inference breaks down. The contribution curve is also shown in blue.

Fig. C.4. Similar to Fig. C.3 for P12.

Fig. C.5. The atmospheric retrieval results for P2 injected into DS2 and preprocessed with SysREM, with the 1D and 2D marginalised posterior distributions of each of the model parameters displayed. The red and blue posterior distributions represent independent subchains, of the same MCMC chain, both converging to similar distributions. The injected values are shown as green vertical/horizontal dashed lines. The T - P profile shown on the right was computed from 10,000 random samples of the MCMC, where the solid red curve shows the median profile, and the grey shaded regions show the 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ contours. The injected profile is shown as a green dashed curve. The cloud deck, located at $\log_{10}(P_{\text{cloud}})$ is highlighted as a blue dotted line. Below this value, the model is truncated, and thus the model inference breaks down. The contribution curve is also shown in blue.

Fig. C.6. Similar to Fig. C.5 for P12.

Fig. C.7. The atmospheric retrieval results for P2 injected into DS2 and preprocessed with MOLECFIT, with the 1D and 2D marginalised posterior distributions of each of the model parameters displayed. The red and blue posterior distributions represent independent subchains, of the same MCMC chain, both converging to similar distributions. The injected values are shown as green vertical/horizontal dashed lines. The T - P profile shown on the right was computed from 10,000 random samples of the MCMC, where the solid red curve shows the median profile, and the grey shaded regions show the 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ contours. The injected profile is shown as a green dashed curve. The cloud deck, located at $\log_{10}(P_{\text{cloud}})$ is highlighted as a blue dotted line. Below this value, the model is truncated, and thus the model inference breaks down. The contribution curve is also shown in blue.

Fig. C.8. Similar to Fig. C.7 for P12.

Fig. C.9. The atmospheric retrieval results for P2 injected into DS3 and preprocessed with SysREM, with the 1D and 2D marginalised posterior distributions of each of the model parameters displayed. The red and blue posterior distributions represent independent subchains, of the same MCMC chain, both converging to similar distributions. The injected values are shown as green vertical/horizontal dashed lines. The T - P profile shown on the right was computed from 10,000 random samples of the MCMC, where the solid red curve shows the median profile, and the grey shaded regions show the 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ contours. The injected profile is shown as a green dashed curve. The cloud deck, located at $\log_{10}(P_{\text{cloud}})$ is highlighted as a blue dotted line. Below this value, the model is truncated, and thus the model inference breaks down. The contribution curve is also shown in blue.

Fig. C.10. Similar to Fig. C.9 for P12.

Fig. C.11. The atmospheric retrieval results for P2 injected into DS3 and preprocessed with MOLECFIT, with the 1D and 2D marginalised posterior distributions of each of the model parameters displayed. The red and blue posterior distributions represent independent subchains, of the same MCMC chain, both converging to similar distributions. The injected values are shown as green vertical/horizontal dashed lines. The T - P profile shown on the right was computed from 10,000 random samples of the MCMC, where the solid red curve shows the median profile, and the grey shaded regions show the 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ contours. The injected profile is shown as a green dashed curve. The cloud deck, located at $\log_{10}(P_{\text{cloud}})$ is highlighted as a blue dotted line. Below this value, the model is truncated, and thus the model inference breaks down. The contribution curve is also shown in blue.

Fig. C.12. Similar to Fig. C.11 for P12.